

The Effectiveness of Know-Want-Learn (KWL) Technique to Improve Students' Reading Comprehension

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this research was to find out whether or not it was effective to use Know-Want-Learn (KWL) technique to improve students' reading comprehension at the Fifth Semester Students of English Education Study Program Universitas Muhammadiyah Palembang. This research was done through Quasi-experimental method including technique for collecting the data and technique for analyzing the data. The population numbers was 36 students, and used the convenience non random sampling. Based on statistic analysis of independent sample t-test, the result of students' score in experimental group and control groups that the value of t-obtained 5.224 was higher than t-test (1.671). It could be concluded that H_0 (Null Hypothesis) was rejected and H_a (Alternative Hypothesis) was accepted. The result of the students' reading comprehension in the posttest of experimental group was (85.30) which were higher than control group which was not through (KWL) with (76.38) as the highest score. It means that the use of this KWL is significance.

Keywords: *Teaching, Known-Want-Learn (KWL), Reading Comprehension*

INTRODUCTION

English has become a global language in this century. As a global language, English is learnt by most people learn English as the requirement to involve in globalization era. English has to be learned by students in order to face this globalization and compete with other people around the world. In Indonesia, English is learnt by the students as a foreign language. According to Patel and Jain (2008), foreign language is the language where the secondary environment is not observed and the people of linguistically foreign societies use such language. There are four skills in learning English, (i.e. listening, reading, speaking and writing). All of the English skills are important, especially reading. Jhonson (2008) stated that reading is the act of linking one idea to another. Putting ideas together to create a sensible whole is the essential part of reading. Meanwhile, Klinger, Vaughn, and Boardman (2007) agued that reading comprehension is the

process of constructing meaning by coordinating a number of complex processes that included word reading, word and world knowledge, and fluency. It means that reading comprehension is an attempt to understand, evaluate and also recognize the author's ideas of reading text and the readers must be able to understand what are the information that given by the researchers.

The students' low ability in reading can be caused by some problems. The teacher does not provide the chance for the students to practice reading more. There were many ways to motivate the students in researching or learning reading. Therefore, the researchers were interested to introduce one technique in teaching reading it will hopefully be interesting for the students. The technique is called *Know-Want-Learn (KWL)*. This technique is created by Ogle (1986). There are three columns, K is the first column telling what the students know about the topic before they read. The second column is W. In this column, the students generate questions about the topic. They tell the teacher about all the things that they want to learn from the topic. The last column is L; here, after reading the text, the students match what they knew in advance and what they wanted to know with what they learnt. Based on the description stated, the researchers can conclude that *Know-Want-Learn (KWL)* technique given many advantages to improve the students' descriptive text of reading comprehension. The first, it can help the students become good readers because they can express their own knowledge. The second, the students can develop the prior knowledge. The third, it helps the students to practice their concentration while they are reading. The last, it offers the opportunities for the students to summarize what they read, when they put the information in their own words, they can understand what they know.

Therefore, the researchers were interested in conducting a research under the title "The Effectiveness of Know-Want-Learn (KWL) Technique to Improve Students' Reading Comprehension at the Fifth Semester Students of English Education Study Program Universitas Muhammadiyah Palembang". The problem of this research was that the students had low score

in reading subject, because reading is one of the difficult skills for many students. There were some problems faced by students in comprehending the text, especially in descriptive text. The problems were that the students may not be good at certain tasks, such as selecting important information, making inferences, and the strategies used by the teachers in teaching which cannot motivate the students.

According to Sulaiman (2017), teaching is such a verbal interaction among the teacher and the students in a good learning sequence or atmosphere. It means that teaching is the process of transferring the knowledge, sharing information, and guiding the learners to do something. In another notion, Daryanto (2010) states that teaching is one component of the competencies of teachers and every teacher should be master and skillfully carry out that teaching. In this context, teaching dealt with the teachers who never stop learning for the students. Brown (2000) states that from the teaching process a teacher can find out how well a technique works, how a student's processes language, how classroom interaction can be improved, how to assess a students' competence, how emotion enter into learning, or how your teaching style affects learners. In brief, teaching was giving the direction, facilities or information about something that they never know before in the learning process. In the process of teaching must be there the good interaction among students and teachers. Because teaching is the concerted sharing of knowledge and experience, and the teachers giving an essential part in helping students to acquire and develop the knowledge and skills they will need in later life and the students have positive change in behavior useful in developing on self and the society.

Reading is most useful and important skill for the people. Hibbard and Wagner (2013), state that reading is a complex behavior including decoding words developing fluency and also improving comprehension. In conclusion, reading is a process of understanding the meaning of printed texts, through the interaction among the reader, text and the context situations.

According to Snow and Chair (2002), reading comprehension as the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language. We use the words extracting and constructing to emphasize both the importance and the insufficiency of the text as a determinant of reading comprehension. Comprehension entails three elements:

1. The reader who is doing the comprehending
2. The text that is to be comprehended
3. The activity in which comprehension is a part.

In this case, reading comprehension is understanding a text that is read, or the process of constructing meaning from a text. Furthermore, Paris and Stahk (2005) stated reading comprehension is the ability to identify meaningful relations between the various parts of a text and between these parts and the readers' background knowledge. From the statements stated, reading comprehension is important because it is a dynamic process in which information from the text and knowledge possessed by the reader interacts to enable the reader to construct meaning before, during, and after reading.

Know Want to Learnt (KWL) Technique

The *Know-Want-Learn (KWL)* technique is a teaching technique that focuses on the involvement of the students and the teacher to take active role in reading and learning (Ogle, 1989). According to Sani (2016) the K-W-L method consists of three steps, namely K step – What I know, W step - What I Want To Learn, L step- What I Learned. K-W-L methods can be applied in critically reading learning. It means that this is the reading strategy will be used to guide the students to comprehend the text by activating students' background knowledge. Uno and

Mohamad (2015) stated that K-W-L strategy gives students the purpose of the reading and an active role before and after reading. This strategy helps students think about the new information received. This strategy can also strengthen the ability to developing questions on various topics and students can also assess their own work.

The Advantages & Disadvantages of Know Want to Learnt (KWL) Technique

Ibrahim (2012) cited in Khaira (2015) stated some advantages & disadvantages of KWL.

The advantages of KWL Technique were as follows:

1. It is appropriate for all education levels from beginners up to advanced.
2. It can be used for all skills but is most suitable for reading skills.
3. It helps students to monitor their comprehension and knowledge.
4. It encourages students to do critical thinking.
5. It makes teacher and students become more interactive in the teaching and learning process.
6. It sets out a purpose for reading. This means that readers have some ideas about the text before reading the whole text and focus to find the important points whilst reading

The disadvantages of KWL are:

1. It is difficult for students with no prior knowledge.
2. It takes time to complete.

3. It is not effective for reading fiction materials.
4. It is not appropriate for readers who are not active thinkers.
5. Students will give up and get bored easily

METHOD

The method in this research used the quasi-experimental method with two groups namely control group and experimental group. The control group was not taught through *Know-Want-Learn (KWL)* technique while the experimental group was taught through *Know-Want-Learn (KWL)* technique. Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun (2012) state that Quasi-experimental designs do not include the use of random assignment and the design of quasi-experimental method that used in this research were pretest-posttest nonequivalent groups design. According to Cohen, Manion, & Morrison (2007), pretest-posttest is one of the most commonly used in quasi-experimental design.

Procedures of Teaching Reading Comprehension in Descriptive Text through *Know-Want-Learn (KWL)* Technique

According to Sani (2016), the procedures for applying the KWL method are:

1. The teacher demonstrates the KWL table and explains how to fill the available column.

Table 1. KWL Table

Know (K)	What (W)	Learn (L)
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2. The teacher demonstrates how to fill the KWL table based on a reading text.

The K column (Know) is filled with the information in the reading text which the

learners already know. The W column (Want to Learn) is filled with the information the learners want to know. The learners should be directed to make inquiries about the content of the text they want to know. The teacher guides the learner to ask questions related with the topic of reading text. In addition, teachers also guide the learners to make priority scales on the questions that really they want the answer. L column is filled with important information in the summary from what they have learned from the text reading. The learners do the reflection from what they have done.

3. The teacher gives the task of the other reading text, in pairs or individuals.

The learners write what they already know from reading text and share information with classmates, and then the learner write the questions about the information what they want to know and share with classmates. After they finish reading, they fill the L column of the KWL table.

4. The teacher closes the lesson by giving directions with the learner about how to use KWL strategy in learning.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Result

The result of the independent sample t-test showed the value of t-obtained was 5.224 at the significant level of $p < 0.05$ (5%) in 2-tailed testing degree of freedom (df) was 70, and the critical value of t-table was 1671. Since the value of t-obtained was higher that the critical value

of t-table so that the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected and the Alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted. Based on the calculation by using SPSS 21.0 program, the mean in the experimental group of pretest score was 72.30 while the mean of post-test score was 85.30. The result of mean from pretest and post-test in experimental group depicted that there was significant differences between the students score pretest and post-test score. The mean in control group of pretest score was 65.47, and the mean of post-test score was 76.38.

In addition, the result of mean from pretest and post-test in the control group revealed that there was the differences between the students pretest score and post-test score but not significant as in the experimental group. Based on the statistical analysis of independent sample t-test, the result of students' score in experimental group and control group where the value of t-obtained 5.224 was higher than t-tangle (1.671). It could be concluded that H_0 (Null Hypothesis) was rejected and H_a (Alternative Hypothesis) was accepted.

Discussion

In process of learning reading comprehension, students faced many problems that affected them in learning comprehension. Thus, the result of pretest and post-test which was too significant. From the data obtained from the research, the researchers found that there were some factors. Those factors were firstly, the problems were that the students may not be good at certain tasks, such as selecting important information and making inferences. Secondly, the researchers observed that English teachers in that school did not provide particular techniques in teaching reading. They use the conventional method in the class. Thus, the students did not enjoy in learning reading comprehension.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings and interpretation in the previous chapter, it could be drawn some

~~conclusions. First, Know-Want-Learn (KWL) Technique in descriptive text was an effective~~

way to develop students' achievement in reading comprehension. Second, *Know-Want-Learn (KWL)* Technique which is related to the text can help students to comprehend the text easily with the text description. Third, the result of the students' reading comprehension in the posttest of experimental group was (85.30) which was higher than the control group which were not through (KWL) (76.38) as the highest score.

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